

Studies on the Synthesis of Heterocyclic Compounds-Part-II. Synthesis of 1-hydroxy-and 1-aryl 3-substituted-4-keto-3, 4-dihydrophthalazines, 1-hydroxy-4-aryl- and 1, 4-dihydroxy-phthalazines

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In the previous communication,¹ the use of polyphosphoric acid (PPA) was reported as a condensing agent in the synthesis of 1-hydroxy-3-substituted-4-keto-3, 4-dihydrophthalazines(I). It has been observed that this agent is very effective in giving these phthalazines in very high yields of clean products in a comparatively shorter time.

Chattaway and Tesh², observed that when N-arylamino-phthalimide was refluxed with alcoholic sodium ethoxide in sealed tube for 12 hours, it was rearranged into (I); 1-hydroxy-3-aryl-3, 4-dihydrophthalazine-4-acetic acids were oxidised by aqueous permanganate³⁻⁵ to (I) at 70-100°; Rowe, Peters and Rangwala⁷ obtained (I) by demethylation of *o*-methyl ether of (I) with hydrobromic acid; Rowe, Le'cutier and Peters⁸ obtained amino derivatives of (I) by reduction of corresponding nitro compounds with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid, Roser⁹,

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

obtained 1-aryl-3-phenyl-4-keto-3, 4-dihydrophthalazine(II) by refluxing the *o*-keto acid and the arylhydrazine in alcohol. Bromberg¹⁰ and Rothenberg¹¹, obtained 1-hydroxy-4-benzylphthalazine(III) and 1-hydroxy-4-phenylphthalazine(III), respectively from benzaldehyde and *o*-benzoylbenzoic acid in hot alcohol with hydrazine hydrate. For the synthesis of 1, 4-dihydroxy phthalazines(IV), various refluxing agents have been used. Drew and Hatt¹², refluxed the reactants for 4 hours with sodium acetate and acetic acid (IV, R=H); Drew and Pearman,¹³ refluxed

3-nitrophthalimide and aqueous hydrazine hydrate for 6 hours (IV, R=5-NO₂) and also for 16 hours an ammoniacal mixture of 6,7-dichloro-1, 4-dihydroxy phthalazine and cuprous iodide for obtaining 6, 7-diamino-1, 4-dihydroxyphthalazine; while 5-methylamino-1, 4-dihydroxyphthalazine and 5, 8-diamino-1, 4-dihydroxyphthalazine were obtained by heating respective phthalimide and hydrazine hydrate (3M) for one hour; Marriott and Robinson¹⁴ refluxed N-arylphthalimide and hydrazine hydrate in boiling pyridine; Huntress, Stainly and Parker¹⁵, heated 1,2,3-NO₂(COOH).C₆H₃.CONHNH₂, at 160° for 12 hours.

Experimental

1-Hydroxy-3-substituted-4-keto-3,4-dihydrophthalazines (I) :

A mixture of phthalic anhydride (0.03M) and mono N-substituted hydrazine (0.03M) was heated on a sand bath with PPA (H₃PO₄ : P₂O₅ : : 12 ml : 20 g) at 160° for 30 minutes and allowed to cool. The mass was decomposed with ice water and crystallised from acetic acid. Phthalazines(I) newly prepared are : 3-amido, m.p. 320°; yield 96% (Found : N, 20.6%. Calcd. for C₉H₇O₂N₂ N, 20.5%); 3-thioamido, m.p. 307°; yield 92% (Found : N, 19.2%, Calcd. for C₉H₇O₂N₂S N, 19.00%).

1-Aryl-3-phenyl-4-keto-3, 4-dihydrophthalazines(II) :

A mixture of *p*-substituted-*o*-arylbobenzoic acid (0.02M) and phenylhydrazine (0.02M) was heated at 100° for 3 minutes and the resulting hydrazone¹⁶ was treated with PPA at 160° for 30 minutes. The cold syrupy mass was decomposed with ice water and crystallised from absolute alcohol. 1-Arylphthalazines(II) newly prepared are : *p*-methylphenyl, m.p. 139°; yield 66% (Found : N, 9.05%. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₈N₂O N, 9.0%); *p*-chlorophenyl, m.p. 165°; yield 70% (Found : N, 8.50%. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈N₂OCl N, 8.40%); *p*-bromophenyl, m.p. 143°; yield 68% (Found : N, 7.65%. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈N₂OBr N, 7.43%).

These phthalazines(II) are colourless microcrystalline solids, insoluble in dilute acid and alkali and soluble in common organic solvents.

1-Hydroxy-4-aryl-phthalazines (III) :

A mixture of *p*-substituted-*o*-arylbobenzoic acid (0.02M) and hydrazine sulphate (0.02M) was heated on a sand bath with PPA at 160° for 30 minutes and the mass was decomposed with ice water and crystallised from acetic acid. Phthalazines (III) prepared are : *p*-methylphenyl, m.p. 248°; yield 88% (Found : N, 11.85%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂N₂O N, 11.90%); *p*-chlorophenyl, m.p. 266°; yield 84% (Found : N, 11.0%. Calcd. for C₁₄H₉N₂OCl N, 10.9%); *p*-bromophenyl, m.p. 266°; yield 86% (Found : N, 9.25%. Calcd. for C₁₄H₉N₂OBr N, 9.3%).

Phthalazines(III) are colourless crystalline solids, sparingly soluble in organic solvents, soluble in dilute alkali, insoluble in dilute mineral acids and are characterised by high melting points. They give cherry red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

1,4-Dihydroxyphthalazines (IV) :

A mixture of phthalimide (0.03M) and 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.032M) was heated on a sand bath with PPA at 220° for 30 minutes and allowed to cool. The mass was decomposed with ice water and crystallised from acetic acid-ethanol (1 : 2) mixture. 6-Benzoylamino-1, 4-dihydroxyphthalazine is newly prepared (m. p. 329°d ; yield 86%).

1, 4-Dihydroxyphthalazines are characterised by high melting points with decomposition, they give reddish-brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Further work along this line is in progress.

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Synthesis of New 5-(2-Oxo-3-Indolinylidene)-3-Benzyl-2-Arylimino-4-Thiazolidinones Derived from 3-Benzyl-2-Arylimino-4-Thiazolidinones

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CONDENSATIONS of 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones with isatin has been reported to yield thioindigoid dyes^{1,2}. Using this approach, new

seventeen 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinylidene)-3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones (3) (Table 1) have been prepared by condensing isatin (1) with 3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones (2) in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid. Various 3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones were obtained from 1-benzyl-3-aryl-2-thioureas and monochloroacetic acid³. These dyes were coloured from deep-orange to dark-red and dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid producing dark coloured solution.

TABLE 1—5-(2-Oxo-3-INDOLINYLIIDENE)-3-BENZYL-2-ARYLIMINO 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (3)

S. No.	Ar.	Yield	m.p. °C	Colour
1.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	77	190	dark-red
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	77	205	dark-red
3.	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	86	212	orange-red
4.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	79	205	orange-red
5.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	70	200	dark-red
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	71	116	dark-red
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	80	95	dark-red
8.	<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl	81	150	dark-red
9.	<i>p</i> Bromophenyl	81	125	dark-red
10.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	91	180	Red
11.	2,5-Dichlorophenyl	73	(decompn.) 135	dark-red
12.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	77	(decompn.) 70	blackish-red
13.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	84	(melts with charring) 75	red
14.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	77	(decompn.) 170	blackish-red
15.	4-Hydroxy-2-methylphenyl	71	(decompn.) 175	dark-red
16.	1-Naphthyl	72	volatile at 260°	red
17.	2-Pyridyl	76	280	bright-red

Experimental

All melting points have been taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.